

MEDIA EXPOSURE AND PARENTAL MEDIATION: IMPLICATIONS ON KINDERGARTNERS' DEVELOPMENTAL SKILLS

Rezzel Mae A. Montecillo

Lourdes College, Cagayan de Oro City, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13291926>

ABSTRACT

As digital technologies permeate communication channels, concerns arise regarding the media's influence on young minds. This study investigated if the different types and durations of media affect cognitive, socio-emotional, language, and physical skills, as well as how parental mediation influence these developments. A total of 100 kindergartners who are enrolled in a public school under the Division of Iligan City school year 2023-2024 participated in the study. The study employed a descriptive–correlational research design and used frequency, percentage, mean, and regression analysis. The Early Childhood Care and Development Checklist and a modified parental mediation questionnaire served as the primary research instruments. Findings revealed that the kindergartners' media exposures and parental mediation do not significantly influence their developmental skills. The kindergartners primarily used media for educational and entertainment purposes, with most spending 1-3 hours weekly, although a significant number also engaged for 7-9 hours per week. The developmental skills of the children were generally highly advanced across all measured domains, indicating effective educational practices. Parental mediation was found to be moderate, often involving setting boundaries and providing guidance rather than engaging in shared media activities. The study's significance extends to various stakeholders. Parents gain insights into media's effects on child development, aiding in making informed decisions about media consumption. Kindergarten teachers can adapt teaching strategies to integrate media effectively into the curriculum. School administrators can develop evidence-based programs and policies to enhance students' developmental skills. Additionally, the study offers a foundation for future research on media exposure and parental mediation.

Keywords: *Media Exposure, Parental Mediation, Developmental Skills, Kindergartners, Media Content*

INTRODUCTION

Today's young children engage with media and technology more than ever before as screens permeate their daily lives. Examining how media exposure shapes capacities across domains like cognition, emotion regulation, language, and physicality is vital. Insights can inform guidance around balanced usage in early childhood to promote healthy academic and life trajectories (Hartnett et al., 2023). Exploring media's effects on kindergartners spans child psychology, education, communication, and media studies. As digital immersion escalates in childhood, caregivers, teachers, and policymakers must grasp how media affects developmental competencies. Substantive studies examined connections between screen media exposure and cognitive development in early childhood. Researchers probe how excessive screen engagement may hinder capacities like attention, academic progress, and language. For instance, Madigan and colleagues (2019) found links between higher screen time and reduced verbal expression in toddlers. Similarly, Tamana et al. (2019) associated preschoolers' screen use with escalated risks of attentional difficulties. Additional work by Watt et al. (2019) tied early television watching to poorer executive function at age five. High ambient screen exposure also appears potentially detrimental – Park et al. (2022) tied it to decreases in caregiver-child interaction quality. According to studies, when parents and children discuss what they're viewing or doing online, it may significantly affect how much media influences children (Lafton et al., 2024). This emphasizes that parents can strengthen their bonds with their children and can give them wise decisions in dealing with gadgets and online. In the end, these conversations are crucial in forming kids' digital habits and media resilience. Despite expansive research, gaps persist around media exposure's attributes and parental mediation's role (Cliff et al., 2018; Zahra et al., 2021). This study aimed to address these knowledge gaps by examining media contents and durations of exposure most likely to shape developmental skills, both constructively and problematically. Kindergartners' complex, evolving media landscape (Sahoo et al., 2021) propels an urgent need to equip caregivers, educators, and policymakers with evidence-based guidance around developmentally appropriate usage.

Framework

This study assumes that kindergartners' media exposure and parental mediation influence their developmental skills. For the researcher to be able to explicate this study and achieve its aim, various theories had also been consulted to support the primary factors. The study is mainly anchored upon two different theories; Attachment Theory and Social Cognitive Theory. Attachment Theory, originally formulated by John Bowlby in 1950, has implications for understanding the impact of media exposure on the developmental skills of kindergartners. This theory emphasizes the importance of secure emotional attachments for healthy development and can be a lens through which we examine how media exposure affects the emotional and social skills of young children.

The second theory where this study can be anchored is on Social Learning Theory (Bandura,1986). This theory posits that children learn by observing and imitating others, and as such, media exposure can serve as a potent source of learning and skill development for young children. Kindergartners are in a critical phase of cognitive, social, and emotional development, and the media they engage with can shape these crucial skills. Positive role models and educational content in media can contribute to the enhancement of their cognitive abilities, social interactions, and emotional intelligence (Chen & Xiao, 2022).

Research Objectives

This study aims to investigate the types and durations of media exposure among kindergartners and examine its influence on their cognitive, socio-emotional, language, and physical skills development. Additionally, it seeks to analyze the role of parental mediation in the media consumption of kindergartners and its impact on their developmental skills. The study provides insights for parents, kindergarten teachers, and school administrators regarding the effects of media on child development and offers guidance on media usage and parental involvement. Furthermore, it aims to establish a foundation for future research on media exposure and parental mediation in early childhood development.

METHODOLOGY

The total number of kindergartners is 100 and 100 parents participated in the study. The study employed a descriptive–correlational research design during the conduct of the research. The researcher utilized a standardized questionnaire from Michael Chia (2018) to determine the extent of media exposure. Also, this research adapted and modified an instrument from Nimrod, Elias, and Lemish (2019) on parents' mediation. As to the level

of developmental skills, the researcher adapted the Early Childhood Care and Development Checklist from the Philippine ECCD Checklist. Frequency, percentage, mean, and regression analysis were used to analyze and interpret the results/findings of the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the frequency distribution of kindergartners' media exposure in terms of types of media content. The data illustrate how often kindergartners engage with different types of media content and highlight the varying levels of media usage among them.

Table 1
Frequency and Percentage of Kindergartners' Media Exposures (Types of Media Content)

Activity	RESPONSE MODES						M	Int.	SD
	Never	1-3 hours / week	3-5 hours / week	5-7 hours / week	7-9 hours / week	9 or more hours / week			
Using media for education / learning (e.g. reading digital e-book learning math via educational apps)	18	39	11	22	7	3	2.70	M	1.34
Using media for entertainment (e.g. watching movies, clips, playing games, listening to music)	17	39	30	7	3	4	2.52	M	1.18
Creating media (e.g. interactive digital toys)	34	28	8	24	5	1	2.41	M	1.36
Communicating (e.g. Video chatting with relatives via facetime/ skype/ messenger)	27	35	21	11	3	3	2.37	M	1.24

The data denote that a good number of 39 kindergartners who engaged for 1-3 hours per week utilized media for educational purposes. However, the kindergartners had varying levels of media exposure for education; 18 kindergartners did not use media for education at all and therefore came up to an average engagement of 2.70 hours per week with moderate variability. In contrast, 22 kindergartners utilized educational media for 5-7 hours per week, and smaller data fell into other categories. That kindergartners spend time using media for education might indicate that receivers consider it useful or efficient at least to some extent; however, to make more definite conclusions concerning the role of media in education, more quantitative results and subjective assessments of learning results should be obtained.

Furthermore, the data on kindergartners' media exposure for entertainment purposes show that 30 kindergartners spent 3-5 hours weekly in entertainment media, including watching movies and playing games, which has a higher engagement, 39 kindergartners engaged for 1-3 hours, 17 kindergartners never used it for entertainment, and a few spent up to 9 or more hours per week, with a mean of 2.52, signifying entertainment media is used less intensively than educational media. However, when it comes to media creation, involving activities like using interactive digital toys, is showing the least common type of media activity among kindergartners, with 34 of them never engaging or never using media for that purpose and only 1 kindergartner dedicating 9 or more hours per week. This implies that while kindergartners are consumers of media content, they are not actively involved in producing or creating media themselves, leading to a wide range of engagement levels within this activity having the highest variability among the categories. The data also shed light on the use of media for communication purposes, such as video chatting with relatives, shows that 35 participants affirmed that they used media for 1 to 3 hours a week to communicate, while 27 kindergartners never used it for this purpose and a small data engage for up to 9 or more hours every week. This clearly explains how at such a tender age the media is used as a tool to facilitate communication as well as interpersonal interactions among kindergartners.

Overall, the data denote that media is primarily used for entertainment and communication purposes among kindergartners, while content creation is not a common activity. A study by Ebbeck, Yim, and colleagues (2019), while primarily focusing on outdoor play, also touched upon the use of media in early childhood education.

Table 2 presents the frequency of kindergartners' media exposure in terms of duration. It highlights the different amounts of time they spend on various media forms.

As regards television usage, the participants are characterized by different exposure times with 20 kindergartners who never watched TV, 24 of them who watched for 1-3 hours or 7-9 hours weekly, and a smaller number of kindergartners who fall into other time categories. The mean usage is 3.10, indicating television is a frequent media form. The findings of the study suggest that parents should limit children's activities to no more than 2 hours of screen time per day excluding the time for doing homework (Legner, 2024). One further important factor is role modeling. The amount of screen time parents and kids spend together is strongly correlated. Such excessive self-watching can be observed when children are brought up in a family where television watching is encouraged (for instance, eating meals in front of the TV, the TV is switched on as soon as the child comes home from school).

Table 2**Frequency and Percentage of Kindergartners' Media Exposures (Duration of Media Consumption)**

Total Average Estimated Time Your Child Used Screen Media Per Week	RESPONSE MODES						Mean	Int.	SD
	Never	1-3 hrs/wk	3-5 hours / week	5-7 hours /week	7-9 hours / week	9 or more hours / week			
Television	20	24	16	11	24	5	3.10	M	1.60
Computer (e.g. desktops, laptops)	57	8	10	17	7	1	2.12	L	1.47
Mobile devices (e.g. smartphones, tablets)	19	25	19	21	7	9	2.99	M	1.53
Video game devices (e.g. console and handheld gaming players, virtual reality headset)	37	18	15	6	9	5	2.27	L	1.56
Blu-ray / DVD / CD / Videotape	50	15	17	11	6	1	2.11	L	1.35
Intelligent / technology toys (e.g. programmable toys)	45	20	20	8	5	2	2.14	L	1.32

The use of computers is found to be low, with 57 kindergartners who did not have computers to use, while 17 of them engaged for 5-7 hours, and a minimal number of kindergartners fall into other categories. Mobile devices, including smartphones and tablets, had a more spread of usage with 25 kindergartners who used them for 1-3 hours, 19 of them used it for 3-5 hours, and 21 kindergartners for 5-7 hours per week. A small number of them reached to 9 or more hours; this raised concerns about the potential impact on early childhood development. Video game devices were less used, with 37 of kindergartners never engaging, and only 5 of them used it for extensively or 9 or more hours. Traditional media formats like Blu-ray, DVD, and Videotape are mainly out of favor, with 50 kindergartners never using them or did not own videotapes, minimal engagement in other time duration, and a low mean of 2.11 hours. This indicates that these media formats are becoming obsolete in the context of modern childhood media consumption. Similarly, intelligent technology toys were also underutilized, with 45 kindergartners having no access to technology toys, and very few using them extensively for 1-3 hours weekly for 20 kindergartners and 3-5 hours weekly for still 20 kindergartners. This results in a low mean usage of 2.14 and moderate variability proposing that these toys are not yet a significant part of kindergartners' media habits.

Table 3 shows the amount of parental mediation engaged in by parents with children in kindergarten in terms of frequency, percentage, and mean. It illustrates the extent of parental mediation regarding children's media use, detailing the frequency and level of parental involvement.

Table 3

Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of Kindergarten Parents' Parental Mediation

Range	Description	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High	5	5.0
3.51-4.50	High	38	38.0
2.51-3.50	Moderate	42	42.0
1.51-2.50	Low	10	10.0
1.00-1.50	Very Low	5	5.0
Total		100	100.0
Overall Mean		3.31	
Interpretation		Moderate	
SD		0.81	

The data revealed that out of 100 parents, only 5 were at a very high level of mediation, while 38 of the parents were actively involved in a high level of mediation.

Furthermore, it reveals that 42 parents had a moderate mediation which means that these parents have a reasonable level of control on the use of the digital media. More so, the data also show that 10 parents were at a low level and 5 at a very low level of mediation, which shows they rarely interfere with their children's use of digital media.

Recent studies support the importance of parental mediation in promoting healthy digital media habits among young children. A study by Livingstone et al. (2021) found that active parental mediation, such as discussing the content and setting boundaries, was associated with reduced screen time and improved digital literacy skills among children aged 4-8 years. Looking at the specific indicators of parental mediation, it is evident that parents tend to have higher levels of involvement in certain areas. For instance, parents scored high in advising their children on the educational or helpful aspects of digital media usage (M=3.78), specifying when their children can play and/or use applications (M=3.69), and specifying how long their children can play and/or use applications (M=3.61). These findings imply that parents recognize the importance of setting boundaries and providing guidance on the appropriate use of digital media. Parents scored moderately in discussing with their children the appropriate use of games, internet, and/or apps (M=3.30), having chats with their children regarding the specific activities they undertake when using digital media (M=3.18), and remaining in the room to monitor the screen when their children use games, websites, and/or apps (M=3.07). These findings indicate that parents could benefit from more active engagement and communication with their children about their digital media experiences. A study by Pérez-Escoda et al. (2021) highlights the importance of parent-child communication in fostering digital literacy skills and promoting responsible media use. However, doing something together with a media device (M=2.75) and engaging in fun activities using a media device, were the lowest among the moderate interpretations. This indicates that parents were less likely to engage in shared digital media activities compared to other mediation practices.

The moderate level of parental mediation can also be attributed to a lack of information on appropriate or efficient ways of mediating. Society should urge parents to be more involved in the way that their children are using digital media hence reducing the effects

that may be brought about by bad use of the devices. Brito et al. (2021) provide information on the need for concerned parents and teachers to ensure the development of young children in the aspects of digital citizenship and media safety.

Table 4 presents a summary of the level of developmental skills among the kindergartners in the study, specifically in the domains of cognitive, socio-emotional, language, and physical development. The mean scores for each domain indicate that the participants exhibited highly advanced skills across all areas.

Table 4

Summary Table of Developmental Skills

Developmental Skills	Mean	Maximum (# of items)	Interpretation	SD
Physical	21.64	24	Highly Advanced	3.92
Socio-Emotional	20.45	23	Highly Advanced	3.45
Cognitive	18.45	21	Highly Advanced	3.82
Language	11.99	13	Highly Advanced	1.84

The mean score for physical development is 21.64 out of a maximum of 24, showing "Highly Advanced" physical skills. Socio-emotional skills have a mean score of 20.45 out of 23, also categorized as "Highly Advanced". Cognitive development is slightly lower but still falls under "Highly Advanced" with a mean score of 18.45 out of 21. Language development, with a mean score of 11.99 out of 13, is again "Highly Advanced," with the least variability.

The interpretation of the mean scores as "Highly Advanced" indicates that the participants demonstrated skills and abilities that are significantly above the expected level for their age group. The highly advanced developmental skills exhibited by the participants underscored the importance of providing high-quality early childhood education that nurtures the holistic development of children. However, the findings highlight also the need for ongoing assessment and monitoring of children's developmental progress. By regularly evaluating children's skills and abilities, educators can identify areas of strength and areas that require additional support (Shine, 2023). This information can then be used to design targeted interventions and adapt the curriculum to ensure that all children have the opportunity to reach their full potential.

Table 5 presents the regression analysis of the influence of different types of media exposure, duration of media exposure, and parental mediation on their developmental skills. Data reveal that the whole model is significant ($F=6.94, p=0.000$).

Table 5

Regression Analysis of the Influence of the Types of Media Exposure, Duration of Media Exposure, and Parental Mediation on the Kindergartners' Developmental Skills

	Unstandardized Coefficients B	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	.647	.050		13.03	.000
Using Media for Education/Learning	.021	.014	.241	1.46	.149
Using Media for Entertainment	.033	.011	.334	3.15**	.002
Creating Media Video Game Devices	-.031	.015	-.354	-2.10*	.038
Blu-ray/ DVD/ CD/ Videotape	.036	.011	.417	3.38	.001
PARENTAL MEDIATION	.027	.013	.186	2.02*	.046
Model Summary					
R = .556	R ² = .309	Adjusted R ² = .265	F = 6.94**	p = .000	

Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. Kindergartners who are exposed to media and whose parents get highly involved in what their children watch, also have high developmental skills. Furthermore, 30.9 percent of the variability in their developmental skills can be accounted for by a combination of their media exposures and parental mediation. The remaining 69.1 percent can be attributed to other factors not covered in this study such as parental education levels and socioeconomic status, which can provide a more stimulating and supportive environment for development. Additionally, the quality of preschool or kindergarten, including teacher qualifications and peer interactions, plays a critical role. Taking the independent variables individually, data reveal that Blu-ray/ DVD/ CD/ Videotape came out as having the highest significant influence on their developmental skills, indicating that for every unit increase in the parental mediation they received, there is a corresponding .036 increase in the children's developmental skills ($B = .036$, $t = 3.38$, $p = .001$). According to Deepa (2020), these tools facilitate the development of cognitive, language, and socio-emotional skills through content that is attractive and promotes academic information and pre-literacy. Readily available at virtual corner stores with easy-to-use, autoplay options, instructional CDs and DVDs are beneficial in the home school setting. It is also important to point out that DVDs can store considerably more information and transfer it with higher speed than CDs making them more preferable for large-scale educational materials." CDs and DVDs are a useful and flexible means of teaching and consolidating certain skills that will be useful both at home and in school for children even without using the internet.

Using Media for Entertainment ranks the second highest impact variable after the Blu-ray/ DVD/ CD/ Videotape. This has a beta value of = 0.334 indicating the fact that for

every one standard deviation in the extent to which media is utilized for entertainment, the developmental skills of the kindergartners also improve by 0.334 standard deviations ($B = .334$, $t = 3.15$, $p = .002$). This signifies a high positive correlation, meaning that an increased amount of media for entertainment is beneficial for the development of children. Furthermore, the significance level (p-value) of 0.002 indicates that this relationship is statistically significant. According to Carson et al. (2021), carefully organizing and balancing educational media with entertainment content resulted in significant enhancements across various cognition domains, including sustained attentiveness, focused attention, and recall achieved under vigilance conditions.

The table also denotes that Creating Media is likely to be significant at a third rank in the significance level. In the following model, it has a standardized coefficient of -0.354 ($B = -0.354$, $t = -2.10$, $p = .038$) point to the fact that creating media correlates positively with the decline in kindergartners' developmental competency. That is; as the time toward the creation of media increases, the developmental skills inherent among the kindergartners are most likely to decrease. The p-value of 0.038 indicates that this relationship is statistically significant since it was giving a significance value. This dispels the possibility of the observed effect being chance in this study as well as in the prior research.

The fourth highest influence on kindergartners' developmental skills is parental mediation. This has a beta of 0.186, indicating that there is an increase of 0.186 in every standard deviation ($B = .186$, $t = 2.02$, $p = .046$). This shows a moderate positive impact, suggesting that greater involvement of parents in mediating their children's media use is associated with better developmental outcomes. The study by Zimmer et al. (2019) highlighted the importance of parental mediation in the digital media usage of kindergarten children, emphasizing controlled and supervised media use. This means that parents need to be involved in their children's media activities by monitoring how much time children spend in media and involved in activities being immersed by their children. Similarly, Anyaegbunam et al. (2019) conducted a study in Nigeria to examine whether parental mediation moderates the relationship between exposure to violent media content and aggressive behavior in adolescents. Their results confirmed the significant moderating role of parental mediation in managing children's media content consumption.

Conclusions

Several implications can be drawn concerning the effects of media exposure and the role of the parents in mediating their children's developmental skills at this early age of readiness for school. The learners achieve impressive results in all the areas, cognitive, socio-emotional, language, and physical skills, which shows that the kindergartners are ready to meet both academic and personal tasks in further stages of their early learning process. In this regard, parental mediation is at a middle level where parents are moderately involved in direct communication with their children concerning media use and in setting guidelines and offering directions, but there is lesser interaction in the co-use of digital devices that could create a stronger bond of parent-child relationship and also in effective mediation. This leads to an agenda for parents to take steps to attend enjoyable media experiences with their children and thus ensure that the technology is

used appropriately. Moreover, media type exposure and parental mediation of these types exert a considerable influence on the kindergartners' development skills. Namely, Blu-ray/DVD/CD/Videotape, entertainment media, creating media, and the active parental mediation processes facilitate these skills. Nevertheless, not all media exposures work to the same advantage therefore pointing out the need to be selective in the usage of Media. In general, it can be stated that the research results stress the importance of appropriate media usage and parents' engagement for the holistic child development of the children. Perhaps, a stronger positive effect on the development of the respective skills can be achieved if parents talk to their child more during media use.

The results of this study align with the Social Cognitive Theory of Albert Bandura, which emphasizes the crucial role of parents in monitoring and guiding their children's activities to ensure that their learning is not hindered. The theory highlights the importance of parental involvement in children's experiences, as it can have a significant impact on their overall development. By actively mediating their children's media consumption, parents can ensure that kindergartners spend an appropriate amount of time using available media at home and engage in activities that promote their cognitive, social, emotional, and physical growth. Similarly, the study also shows a link with John Bowlby's Attachment Theory, with emphasis on the child's attachment to media. Bowlby's theory focuses on the idea that a child with attachment to a certain person who makes him/her feel protected is critical in his/her development. Reflecting on media as an attachment figure, one can touch upon the patterns in children's attachment to media content and devices, as well as the role of development and parental mediation. Kindergartners utilize the media most in the areas of education and entertainment with exposure to media ranging from 1-3 hours to 7-9 hours in one week. This denotes that media is an essential part of their daily existence and thus could serve as media as an object of attachment serving the basic functions of attachment figures in those people's lives. As with objects of attachment, children desire certain interactions and stimulating media experiences that can even be compared to basic needs for the care of parents.

Overall, the present study underscores the critical role of parental mediation and controlled media exposure in fostering the developmental skills of kindergarten learners. As foundational abilities, these skills lay the groundwork for children's future success and well-being. Promoting a balanced approach to media usage, encouraging active parental involvement, and implementing supportive policies and practices, can create an environment that nurtures the holistic development of young children in the digital age.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author of this study obtained the respondents' informed consent and informed them of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any time. Anonymity of the respondents was maintained and the respondents' well-being was safeguarded. There was no conflict of interest in the conduct of the study. Plagiarism and bias in the interpretation of the findings were strictly avoided and the results were used purely for research.

REFERENCES:

- Anyaegbunam, C. L., Okorie, N., & Ndubuisi-Okolo, P. (2019). Parental mediation, exposure to violent media content and aggressive behavior among adolescents in Anambra State, Nigeria. *African Journal of Children and Media*, 1(1), 1-19.
- Bergqvist-Norén et al., 2022
- Brito, R., Dias, P., & Oliveira, G. (2021). The importance of parents' mediation strategies on children's digital literacy competencies. *Journal of Children and Media*, 15(3), 323-339. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17482798.2020.1832143>
- Chen & Xiao, 2022
- Carson, V., Lee, E. Y., Hewitt, L., Jennings, C., Hunter, S., Kuzik, N., Stearns, J. A., Unrau, S. P., Poitras, V. J., Gray, C., Adamo, K. B., Janssen, I., Okely, A. D., Spence, J. C., Timmons, B. W., Sampson, M., & Tremblay, M. S. (2017). Systematic review of the relationships between physical activity and health indicators in the early years (0-4 years). *BMC Public Health*, 17(5). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-017-4860-0>
- Chen, P., & Xiao, X. (2022). Explaining interactive media use among children from a social cognitive perspective. *Journal of Children and Media*, 16(1), 61-77. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17482798.2020.1867035>
- Chia, M., Tay, L. Y., & Chua, T. B. K. (2018). The development of an online surveillance of digital media use in early childhood questionnaire - SMALLQ® - for Singapore. <http://mjssm.me/?sekcija=article&artid=185>
- Cliff, D. P., Howard, S. J., Radesky, J. S., McNeill, J., & Vella, S. A. (2018). Early childhood media exposure and self-regulation: Bidirectional longitudinal associations. *Academic Pediatrics*, 18(7), 813–819. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acap.2018.06.006>
- Deepa (2020)
- Deepa, K. (2020). CD and DVD. <https://deepaeducation.blogspot.com/2020/08/cd-and-dvd.html>
- Ebbeck, M., Yim, H. Y. B., & Warriar, S. (2019). Early childhood teachers' views and teaching practices in outdoor play with young children in Singapore. *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 47(3), 265-273. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10643-018-0924-8>
- Hartnett, A.L., Stuart, D., Munzer, T. & Lipkin, P.H. (2023). Smart Tech Use During Early Childhood and Child Health Outcomes. *JAMA Network Open*, 6(1), e2243677. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2022.43677>
- Hu et al. (2021)
- Lafton, T., Wilhelmsen, J. E. B., & Holmarsdottir, H. B. (2024). Parental mediation and children's digital well-being in family life in Norway. *Journal of Children and Media*, 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17482798.2023.2299956>
- Livingstone et al. (2021)
- Legner, L. (2024, June 7). Kids' screen time: How much is too much? | OSF HealthCare. OSF HealthCare Blog. <https://www.osfhealthcare.org/blog/kids-screen-time-how-much-is-too-much/>
- Livingstone, S., Mascheroni, G., & Staksrud, E. (2021). European research on children's internet use: Assessing the past and anticipating the future. *New Media & Society*, 23(5), 1263-1280. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444820929480>
- Madigan, S., Browne, D. T., Racine, N., Mori, C., & Tough, S. (2019). Association Between Screen Time and Children's Performance on a Developmental Screening Test. *JAMA Pediatrics*, 173(3), 244. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamapediatrics.2018.5056>
- Nimrod, G., Elias, N., & Lemish, D. (2019). Measuring mediation of children's media use. *International Journal of Communication*, 13(1932–8036/20190005). <https://ijoc.org/index.php/ijoc/article/viewFile/10237/2535>
- Park, E., Miller, E., Lombrozo, T., & Zosh, J. M. (2022). Hey Google, do unicorns exist? Smart speakers impair parent-child conversations during joint media engagement. *Journal of Children and Media*, 16(2), 131–151. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17482798.2021.1946238>
- Pérez-Escoda et al

- Pérez-Escoda, A., Iglesias-Onofrio, M., & Sánchez-Gómez, M. C. (2021). Parental mediation and digital skills in primary school students in Spain. *Comunicar*, 29(68), 49-59. <https://doi.org/10.3916/C68-2021-04>
- Sahoo, S., Padhy, S.K., Singh, S., Sahu, T., Meher, C., Brooks, J., Bhattacharya, J.P., Sarkar, S., & Grover, S. (2021). Screen Time in School-Age Children Before and During COVID-19 Lockdown. *Indian Journal of Pediatrics*, 88(1), 53–56. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12098-020-03465-1> Shine, 2023
- Shine, R. A. (2023, April 14). Why monitoring your child's development is so important - Children's National. Rise and Shine by Children's National. <https://riseandshine.childrensnational.org/why-monitoring-your-childs-development-is-so-important/>
- Tamana, S. K., Ezeugwu, V., Chikuma, J., Lefebvre, D. L., Azad, M. B., Moraes, T. J., Subbarao, P., Becker, A. B., Turvey, S. E., Sears, M. R., Carson, V., Rasmussen, C., Pei, J., & Mandhane, P. J. (2019). Screen-time is associated with inattention problems in preschoolers: Results from the CHILDBirth cohort study. *PLOS ONE*, 14(4), Article e0213995. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0213995>
- Watt, E., Fitzpatrick, C., Derevensky, J. L., & Pagani, L. S. (2019). Too Much Television? Prospective Associations Between Early Childhood Televiewing and Later Cognitive and Psychosocial Outcomes. *Archives of Pediatrics & Adolescent Medicine*, 173(10), 968–975. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamapediatrics.2019.2104>
- Zahra, A., Hussain, S., & Khan, M. A. (2021). Technology use during COVID-19 and development of preschool children in Pakistan. *Early Child Development and Care*, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03004430.2021.1877058>
- Zimmer, M., Christakis, D. A., & Meltzoff, A. N. (2007). Television and DVD/video viewing in children younger than 2 years. *Archives of pediatrics & adolescent medicine*, 161(5), 473–479. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archpedi.161.5.473>